

Studies on Triorthoperiodato Tetracobaltic(III) Acid, $\text{H}_3\text{Co}_4\text{I}_3\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_{12}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$

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The compound $\text{H}_3\text{Co}_4\text{I}_3\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_{12}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been prepared and studies have been made on its oxidising, conductance, magnetic and semi-conducting properties.

THE compound triorthoperiodato tetracobaltic acid, $\text{H}_3\text{Co}_4\text{I}_3\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_{12}\cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, has been prepared following known method¹ and given the composition $\text{H}_3\text{Co}_4\text{I}_3\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_{12}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In this compound, the periodate ion, a strong oxidising agent, has stabilised the higher valency of cobalt(+3). This dark green polynuclear compound is a potent oxidising agent and is quite stable. As systematic studies of this compound have not yet been made, so we have studied its oxidising, acidic, conductance magnetic and semi-conducting properties.

Experimental

The compound $\text{Na}_3[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}(\text{CO}_3)_3]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was first prepared² and dissolved in appropriate amount of HClO_4 to which was added a known amount of sodium meta-periodate. The green crystalline product thus obtained was dissolved in hot (80°) water and crystallised from 2M HClO_4 after allowing the solution to stand for several days. After two such precipitations the crystals were collected and analysed.

Estimation :

Cobalt was estimated by the sulphate method. Iodine was analysed following the method outlined by Willard and Furman³. Water was determined from the weight loss at 140°. Hydrogen was estimated by Thomas CH Analyzer 35.

Found : Co = 21.13%, I = 34.09%, H_2O = 19.36%, H = 2.41%
Calculated for $\text{H}_3\text{Co}_4\text{I}_3\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_{12}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Co = 20.96%, I = 33.89%, H_2O = 19.22%, H = 2.40%

The polynuclear compound is dark green both in the solid state and in aqueous solution. For the

determination of the oxidation state and total quantity of oxidising agents present, the following titrations were carried out :

About 0.030 gm of the compound was dissolved in about 75 ml of water, 100 ml 2(N) H_2SO_4 and 3 gm solid KI were added and the solution was titrated with 0.025(N) $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution at room temp. using starch as an indicator. It required 27.85 equivalents of sodium thiosulphate to titrate the liberated iodine per mole of the sample corresponding to the reduction of Co(III) to Co(II) and of periodate to iodine⁴.

In another operation, 0.0283 gm of the compound was dissolved in 60 ml water, 0.15 gm KCN was added. Then 5 ml formalin, 60 ml 2(N) H_2SO_4 and about 3 gm solid KI were added and the liberated iodine was titrated with 1.05 (N/40) $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution at room temperature to the starch-iodide end point. It required 23.90 equivalents of sodium thiosulphate solution per mole of the compound corresponding to the reduction of per-iodate to iodine.

Titration was also carried out following that of Lister and Yoshino⁴. 0.0523 gm of the compound was dissolved in 50 ml water ; 50 ml 2(N) H_2SO_4 , 25 ml 1.02 (M/40) Mohr solution in 1(N) H_2SO_4 was

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added and then titrated back at room temperature with 1.025 (N/40) $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution using Barium diphenylamine sulphonate as indicator. 9.93 moles of Fe^{++} were required per mole of the compound corresponding to the reduction of Co(III) to Co(II) and of periodate to iodate.

All these show cobalt is present in the trivalent and iodine in the heptavalent state.

Potentiometric Titration :

The acid was titrated with ferrous sulphate in acid solution potentiometrically. The cell used was $Pt/H_3Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12} \cdot 6H_2O$ in 1(N) H_2SO_4/Hg_2Cl_2 in saturated KCl/Hg . The results given below are the voltages relative to the calomel (satd.) electrode.

Titration was carried out with 2.64×10^{-4} (M) $H_3Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12} \cdot 6H_2O$ in 1.0(N) H_2SO_4 against 0.0214(M) Mohr's salt at 29.5°. E.m.f. shown are in millivolts. Volume of Mohr added in ml and their corresponding change in e.m.f. are shown in parentheses. 0 ml (109.5), 0.25 ml (110.0), 0.50 (111.5), 0.75(111.8), 1.0(113.0), 1.50(114.0), 2.0(115.0), 2.5 (118.3), 3.0(125.5), 3.5(130.2), 4.0(140), 4.2(145.1), 4.4(150), 4.6(180.3), 4.8(220.2), 4.9(275.1), 5.0(335.0), 5.20(350), 5.40(365), 5.50(375), 6.0(385.6) 7.0(390), 7.5(405), 8.0(410), 8.5(420).

This shows that the compound is reduced at one step acting as a complex ion, so that there is only one inflection point. The potential where the compound is full neutralised is 280 m. volt and the half-neutralisation voltage is 118 (mv), corresponding to apparent standard electrode potential relative to calomel, which may not be the true equilibrium potential. A reaction of this sort involving transfer of oxygen may well be a slow reaction, evident from the fact that the system attains equilibrium very slowly. The whole system is reduced in one step, so that we get the average standard reduction potential value corresponding to the reduction of Co^{+3} to Co^{+2} and of IO_4^- to IO_3^- species simultaneously⁴.

However, the number of molecules of Mohr salt reacting is quite definite. The inflection occurs at 10 molecules per molecule of the periodate species. This is what is required by the equation.

Conductometric Titration :

Titration of a 8.2×10^{-4} (M) solution of the acid with standard 0.03(M) NaOH solution in a Philips conductance bridge showed two breaks—one very

sharp and the other weak corresponding to the neutralisation of two protons. The third dissociation being very weak could not be followed conductometrically.

pH Titration with Standard Sodium Hydroxide Solution :

For this titration 1.53×10^{-3} (M) solution of the above polynuclear acid was prepared and titrated with standard caustic soda solution in an ELICO pH-meter using 2(M) $NaNO_3$ bridge with glass electrode of 0-13 pH range. From the data, $\Delta pH/\Delta v$ values were calculated and plotted against 'v'-the volume of alkali.

Conductance Measurement :

Conductometric measurements in aqueous solution were carried out in a Philips conductance bridge. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CONDUCTOMETRIC MEASUREMENT Temp. 28°C			
Dilutions in litres per mole	pH of the solution	Resistance (ohms)	Molar conductivity (mho-cm ²)
500	2.20	0.08×10^4	674
750	2.41	0.11×10^4	736.4
1000	2.52	0.135×10^4	792
1500	2.63	0.190×10^4	840
2000	2.80	0.23×10^4	923.2

From the results it appears that the conductivity value increases gradually with dilution. The acid behaves as a weak electrolyte. The abnormally high value of molar conductance at 1024 dilution cannot be explained for a compound of this type which should ionise as $H_3A \rightleftharpoons 3H^+ + A^{3-}$ and give evidence for four ions in the solution. The molecule may contain some labile ions which is responsible to give high conductance value.

Magnetic Measurement :

Magnetic susceptibility measurement of the solid compound was carried out in a Guoy magnetic balance. The compound is slightly paramagnetic and molar susceptibility value has been found to be 137.7×10^{-8} at 20°. The pure compound would have been diamagnetic. This residual paramagnetism may arise due to the presence of some cobaltous ion in the compound.

Study of Semi-Conducting Property :

Semi-conducting property of the acid $H_3 [Co_4I_3O_{24}H_{12}] \cdot 6H_2O$ was studied employing sandwich cell technique with stainless steel and conducting glass electrode. Current was measured in an Electrometer Amplifier—EA 815 of E.C.I.L. (India). Heating rate 30V variac in the range 20° to 50°.

The results show that the compound possesses semi-conducting property with low activation energy of 0.16615 eV. The compound of course conducts high current. The discrepancy between high current and such low activation energy cannot however be explained from this study. It may be due to the presence of some impurity in the form of Co^{3+} ions in the original compound, which facilitates the electron transfer from valence band to conduction band. Results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	$1000/T^{\circ}\text{K}$	Current (amp.)
22.25	3.386	8.9×10^{-7}
23.45	3.373	9.7×10^{-7}
25.50	3.35	1.09×10^{-6}
30.45	3.295	1.45×10^{-6}
32.80	3.270	1.67×10^{-6}
35.20	3.244	1.91×10^{-6}
37.50	3.22	2.20×10^{-6}
41.00	3.184	2.66×10^{-6}
43.3	3.161	3.10×10^{-6}
46.9	3.125	3.74×10^{-6}
49.3	3.102	4.20×10^{-6}

Results and Discussion

Although the acid has earlier been given the composition $\text{H}_3\text{Co}_4\text{I}_3\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_{12} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, our study shows it to be $\text{H}_3\text{Co}_4\text{I}_3\text{O}_{24}\text{H}_{12} \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is a dark green crystalline compound which retains its green colour in aqueous solution. It possess both acidic and oxidising properties. The acid is a weak tri-basic one although conductometric titration can

reveal the presence of only two protons. The compound can be reduced by various reducing agents. The presence of Co(III) and I(VII) can be demonstrated from its oxidising behaviour. The reduction product depends upon the reducing agent chosen. It is stable both in the solid state and in solution. Oxidising agent with such high molecular weight (formula weight is 1124) can be used as a primary standard in analytical chemistry. The end point is sharp and colourless. The compound is reduced in one step. The polynuclear acid contains some cobaltous ion—which has been reflected in its oxidising, magnetic and semi-conducting properties. The conductance behaviour is rather abnormal.

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